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Abstract:	<p>Objective To know the rotavirus burden associated with acute gastroenteritis along with circulating genotypes among under-five children and to find out possible associations with different demographic and clinical predictors in a tertiary care teaching hospital in Bhubaneswar, Odisha.</p> <p>Methods A prospective acute gastroenteritis surveillance conducted from February 2016 to June 2019 at a tertiary care pediatric hospital in Bhubaneswar has enrolled 850 children under five years of age. The stool samples were tested for VP6 antigen of rotavirus by enzyme immunoassay (EIA) and hemi-nested multiplex PCR to find out VP7 (G type) and VP4 (P type) genes. The data was presented using mean \pm SD, median (IQR) along with frequencies and percentages.</p> <p>Results Rotavirus positivity was found in 246 children (28.9%) with male : female ratio of 3:1. An increasing trend of rotaviral diarrheal cases was seen during the winter months. History of vomiting for 2 d, age group of 12–23 mo, and fever were significantly associated with rotavirus diarrhea having odd ratios of 1.80 (95% CI , 1.48, and 1.69, respectively. Among the genotypes, G3 and P8 were found to be most common in the present study.</p> <p>Conclusion With the introduction of Rotavac in the state the overall rotaviral distribution has significantly changed. Children of 6–23 mo were the most affected age group in the study indicating the necessity of this vaccine in the early months of life.</p>	
Response to Reviewers:	We have modified the manuscript as desired. Methodology part was rewritten to avoid	

similarity with our previous publications. References are cited as per the journal. We are ready to oblige for any more modification needed.

With regards

Nirmal Kumar Mohakud

Surveillance and Molecular Characterization of Rotavirus Strains

Circulating in Odisha, India after Introduction of Rotavac

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Abstract

Objective To know the rotavirus burden associated with acute gastroenteritis along with circulating genotypes among under-five children and to find out possible associations with different demographic and clinical predictors in a tertiary care teaching hospital in Bhubaneswar, Odisha.

Methods A prospective acute gastroenteritis surveillance conducted from February 2016 to June 2019 at a tertiary care pediatric hospital in Bhubaneswar has enrolled 850 children under five years of age. The stool samples were tested for VP6 antigen of rotavirus by enzyme immunoassay (EIA) and hemi-nested multiplex PCR to find out VP7 (G type) and VP4 (P type) genes. The data was presented using mean \pm SD, median (IQR) along with frequencies and percentages.

Results Rotavirus positivity was found in 246 children (28.9%) with male : female ratio of 3:1. An increasing trend of rotaviral diarrheal cases was seen during the winter months. History of vomiting for 2 d, age group of 12–23 mo, and fever were significantly associated with rotavirus diarrhea having odd ratios of 1.80 (95% CI , 1.48, and 1.69, respectively. Among the genotypes, G₃ and P₈ were found to be most common in the present study.

Conclusion With the introduction of Rotavac in the state the overall rotaviral distribution has significantly changed. Children of 6–23 mo were the most affected age group in the study indicating the necessity of this vaccine in the early months of life.

Keywords Rotavirus, Under five, Vaccine, Diarrheal disease, Bhubaneswar, Acute gastroenteritis, G3P8

Introduction

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4 Rotavirus is the leading cause of childhood diarrhea [1, 2]. Belonging to the family
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6 Reoviridae, the virus has 9 species denoted by alphabets from A to I. Rotavirus-A is the cause of
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8 more than 90% of human cases while, rest of the species can be seen in pigs and birds.
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10 Rotavirus-A is further classified by binary system of rotavirus classification on account of the
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12 capsid proteins of outer layer namely VP4 (P type) and VP7 (G type) [3–6]. Diarrheal disease
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14 was fifth leading cause of mortality among 0–5 y children globally from 1990–2016 in 195
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16 countries. Among these, rotavirus was the leading cause of mortality with 1,28,515 deaths [7]. In
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18 collaboration with UNICEF (United Nation Children’s Fund), the WHO had launched the
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20 Integrated Global Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Pneumonia and Diarrhoea
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22 (GAPPD) to end all preventable childhood deaths by 2025 by preventing two leading cause of
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24 deaths in children viz. pneumonia and diarrhea. The specific goals for Diarrhea was to reduce
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26 under-5 mortality too less than 1 per 1000 live births [8]. As, rotavirus plays a major role in
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28 majority of these deaths, the world has already started emphasizing on its prevention with the
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30 help of simple preventive measures like vaccination. Hence, WHO had emphasized to include
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32 such vaccines in all national immunization programs.
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41 In India, as per the 2011 indian birth cohort estimates, over 11 million episodes of acute
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43 gastroenteritis in under five children and around 78000 deaths were caused due to rotavirus
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45 diarrhea [9]. According to a study done by ICMR Bhubaneswar, before the addition of rotavirus
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47 in National Immunization Schedule (NIS), the prevalence of rotavirus disease among childhood
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49 diarrhea cases was found to be 54%. The prevalent strains being G1P8 followed G2P4 and the
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51 most commonly affected age group was found to be from 7–12 mo [10]. Rotavac containing
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53 monovalent strain G9P11 (also known as 116E) [11] live, attenuated, oral vaccine is
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55 manufactured by Bharat Biotech with an efficacy of 56.4% and 49% in the first and second year
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4 of life, respectively for severe non vaccine rotavirus gastroenteritis. Rotavac vaccine was
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6 introduced in NIS in India with the brand name Rotavac from April 2016 [10]. Before its
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8 introduction, the community was largely dependent on self-purchased vaccine.
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11 Few studies from Bhubaneswar were in the pre-vaccination era and the present study was
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13 done to determine the rotaviral characteristics of the circulating strains in the post-vaccination
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15 era. Therefore, surveillance is necessary for detecting possible changes of circulating strains in
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17 this region. This study was conducted to know the rotavirus burden associated with acute
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19 gastroenteritis along with circulating genotypes among under five children and to find out
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21 possible associations with different demographic and clinical predictors in a tertiary care
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23 teaching hospital in Bhubaneswar, Odisha.
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29 **Material and Methods**

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32 This prospective observational study was done in under-five children admitted for acute
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34 gastroenteritis (AGE) in the pediatrics ward of School of Medicine, Bhubaneswar from the
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36 month of February 2016 to June 2019. Children presenting with diarrhea for at least six hours
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38 were eligible for enrollment. Among the eligible candidates, the authors had enrolled children
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40 whose guardian or parent gave a written informed consent for the study. For all enrolled
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42 children, an attempt was made to collect stool sample within 48 h of admission. In this manner,
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44 the authors had collected stool samples of 850 participants. Children older than 5 y or with
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46 episodes of dysentery or those who were not falling under the AGE criteria (of more than 3 stool
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48 episodes in 24 h period) were excluded. Clinical assessment was done based on episodes of
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50 diarrhea, vomiting, fever and dehydration. Vesikari score was used for assessing the severity of
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52 diarrhea with mild being 0–5, moderate 6–10, severe 11–15 and 16–20 for very severe disease.
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4 Stool sample was collected from each enrolled child and stored in ice lined refrigerator room of
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6 the facility. The samples were delivered to CMC Vellore once a month.
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10 At first, screening of these collected samples were done for identification of VP6 antigen.
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12 This was done with the help of enzyme immunoassay or EIA (Cincinnati, PremierTMRotaclone,
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14 Meridian Biosciences Inc.). Manufacturer's instruction was thoroughly followed in every process
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16 and positivity report was given for samples with OD value ≥ 0.150 . These positive samples were
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18 sent for genotyping by PCR. For RNA (viral) extraction Qiagen, QIAcubeHT methods were
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20 used. These automated method utilizes 20 % (W/V) stool suspension or 0.2 g of stool in 1 mL of
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22 minimum essential medium (MEM). This RNA (viral) was then converted to complementary
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24 DNA sequence and taken as a template, for the detection of genes with the help of heminested
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26 multiplex PCR technique using the required oligonucleotide primers [2, 12, 13]. In this way we
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28 had detected VP4 (P-type) and VP7 (G-type) in the given stool samples. Primers were included
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30 in PCR for identifying VP4 (P4, P6, P8, P9, P10, P11) and VP7 genotypes (G1, G2, G3, G4, G8,
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32 G9, G10, G12). A conventional VP6 PCR was used, in cases we were unable to detect any
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34 rotavirus genotype from stool.
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42 In those stool samples, where we could not detect any genotypes by PCR, a conventional
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44 VP6 PCR was used to identify rotavirus positivity.
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48 The data were analyzed by STATA-13 (StataCorp, USA). The mean \pm SD, median (IQR)
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50 along with frequencies and percentages were used to present the data. Independent student t test
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52 was used to compare the means of categorical variables. Univariate logistic regression analysis
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54 was used to estimate the predictors of rotavirus diarrhea. The *p* value of < 0.05 was considered
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56 statistically significant. Ethical committee clearance was obtained from KIMS, Bhubaneswar
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58 and CMC Vellore before the commencement of the study.
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4 **Results**
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7 The present study had enrolled a total of 850 children. Around 246 children (28.9%) were
8 found to be suffering from rotavirus diarrheal disease. The positivity percentage was highest in
9 the year 2019 (46.6%) and lowest in the year 2017 (16.3%) (Table 1).
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15 Figure 1 depicts the trend of diarrheal diseases throughout the study period. There was an
16 accumulation of positive cases during the winter months, whereas the summer months were
17 predominantly occupied with rotavirus-negative diarrhea cases. Monthwise distribution from
18 2016–19 shows that November to March accounts for majority of positive cases (186 cases —
19 75.6%) and the peak being the December to February.
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28 The maximum number of rotavirus-positive cases were observed in the age group 12–23
29 mo with 107 (33.6%) cases followed by 6–11 mo with 70 (33.7%) cases. The overall percentage
30 positivity in both age groups was almost similar in each group. In 0–5 y, 6 mo to 2 y were the
31 most affected age group for rotavirus (177 out of 246 positive cases) (Fig. 2).
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39 Among the present study participants, females were more commonly affected than males
40 with nearly one in every three female children with diarrhoea were found to be positive for
41 rotavirus (32.1%). Observing demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants, it was
42 found that age group of 0–5 mo, 12–23 mo, history of vomiting for 2 d and fever were
43 significantly associated with rotavirus diarrhea (Table 2).
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51 The Table 3 shows the overall genotypic distribution in rotavirus-positive cases among
52 study participants. In the present study, G3P[8] was found to be more prevalent with more than
53 half of the positive cases indicating the strain in their stool samples. The yearwise distribution
54 also showed similar picture with G3P[8] being the most commonly encountered strain in stool
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4 analysis of rotavirus cases with 46.4% (32 out of 69 cases), 55.3% (26 out of 47 cases), 68.3%
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6 (56 out of 82 cases), 64.6% (31 out of 48 cases) in 2016–19, respectively. In 2016–17 and 2018–
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8 19, G1P[8] and the mixed variant were second most common strains associated with rotavirus
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10 cases. Over the period of time G1P[8] strains had declined and number of mixed genotypes had
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12 increased. It was found that G2P[4] and G9P[4] strains were also in increasing trend from the
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14 year 2016 to 2019.
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19 **Discussion**

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23 Episodes of Rotavirus diarrhea was found predominantly in the winter season in the
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25 present study. Similar observations were made by previous studies too. After which, many had
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27 considered using the term “winter diarrhea” for this disease [14–16]. The rotavirus detection rate
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29 in this study was found to be 28.9% which is similar to the findings of a study done in 7 sites (6
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31 states) of India, with a range of rotavirus positivity from 23.5% to 49.1% [9]. The prevalence of
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33 rotavirus in diarrheal cases was identified as 54.8% which had indicated the high presence of
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35 wild virus in the Bhubaneswar city between September 2013 and May 2015 [10]. With no
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37 specific vaccine against rotavirus in the national program and with high burden of cases in the
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39 community the Government of India launched Rotavac in the country from Bhubaneswar. Now
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41 after three years of Rotavac immunization in UIP shedule there is a declining trend of rotaviral
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43 diarrheal cases.
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50 Presence of vomiting and fever were found significantly associated with rotavirus diarrhea.

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52 Studies by Panicker et al., Konno et al., Bhandari et al. and Ansari et al. showed that fever and
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54 vomiting are often associated with rotavirus [17–20]. Among under-five children age group of
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56 12–23 were significantly associated with rotavirus illness in the present study. An Indian Council
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58 of Medical Research (ICMR) study also found a higher prevalence of rotavirus disease among
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4 children aged 13–24 mo with 59.7% followed by 7–12 mo with 56.6%, which was similar to the
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6 present study which found 50.7 % prevalence in both age groups [10, 21].
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10 G3P[8] (58.9%) was found to be commonest strain causing rotavirus diarrhea in the
11 present study which was followed by GP-mixed (17.5%) and G1P[8] (13.4%). In previous
12 studies, G3P[8] was considered as the emerging strain. Many studies had found G1P[8] to be
13 most prevalent in causing disease but now, the scenario has shifted to G3P[8] [3, 9]. In a joint
14 study done by RMRC and ICMR Bhubaneswar during the pre-vaccination era, it was observed
15 that before the inception of Rotavac, G1P[8] was the most common genotype (62.2%) circulating
16 in the community [10]. This change or conversion may had come after the introduction of
17 rotavirus vaccine (Rotavac) in the country in April 2016. This may also indicate a cross
18 protection of G9P[11] vaccine, which needs further research and analysis. This changing pattern
19 of genotype distribution suggests the continuous need for rotavirus disease surveillance and
20 vaccine effectiveness studies for adequate management of rotavirus diarrhea in this region.
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37 The absence of differentiation and further comparison of vaccine virus and wild G9 virus
38 could have given us more in depth knowledge. The association between severity of side effects,
39 like diarrhea with particular strains of rotavirus was also not assessed completely. Still, this study
40 had found out the circulating pattern of rotavirus strains in Odisha. The present study was a part
41 of large-scale surveillance of rotavirus across the country monitored by Christian Medical
42 College, Vellore. The use of a single tool and analysis across all the sites could serve as a
43 yardstick for future researches.
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55 **Conclusions**

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4 The rotavirus positivity was found to be 29.2% and 6–23 mo age group being the most
5 affected. The disease was mostly prevalent in winter months. Our study had found a change in
6 genotypic distribution with G3P[8] being the prevalent strain. The vaccination status of these
7 children with the identification and differentiation of wild and vaccine virus among them could
8 have given more conclusive statement while considering the age of the participants. Nonetheless,
9 the inception of vaccine did influence the overall frequency as well as distribution in the
10 community. Hence, the use of such vaccine is highly recommended.
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37 **Authors' Contributions** VG, NKM, SR: Study design, manuscript development; MKN, NM:
38 Data acquisition, management and manuscript development; VG, NKM, NM, RK, SR: Data
39 analysis, literature review and manuscript writing; All authors approved the final manuscript.
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44 NKM will act as guarantor of the study.
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48 **Conflict of Interest** None.
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Table 1 Distribution of rotavirus test positive cases by year of surveillance (2016 to 2019)

Year	No. of children eligible for enrolment (from Diarrhea logbook)	No. of children enrolled N (%)	No. of children with stool-specimens available	Children with rotavirus-positive specimens by enzyme immunoassay	
				Number	Percentage
2016	207	192 (92.57)	192	69	35.9
2017	352	288 (81.82)	288	47	16.3
2018	361	268 (74.24)	267	82	30.7
2019	145	103 (71.03)	103	48	46.6
Total	1065	851 (79.91)	850	246	28.9

Table 2 Demographic, clinical, and outcome characteristics of under-5 children with rotavirus gastroenteritis, (KIMS, Bhubaneswar) from 2016 to 2019

Characteristics	Rotavirus Positive	Rotavirus Negative	OR (95% CI)	P-Value
Gender				
Male	147 (27.5%)	388 (72.5%)	Ref	Ref
Female	99 (32.1%)	209 (67.9%)	1.25 (0.92 – 1.70)	0.153
Age Group				
0–5 mo	9 (11.1%)	72 (88.9%)	0.37 (0.17 – 0.78)	0.009*

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6–11 mo	70 (33.7%)	138 (66.3%)	1.49 (0.99 – 2.24)	0.058
12–23 mo	107 (33.6%)	211 (66.4%)	1.48 (1.02 – 2.16)	0.037*
24–59 mo	60 (25.4%)	176 (74.6%)	Ref	Ref
Duration of diarrhea in days				
0–4	233 (29.4%)	560 (70.6%)	Ref	Ref
5	7 (22.6%)	24 (77.4%)	0.70 (0.30 – 1.65)	0.416
6–7	6 (31.6%)	13 (68.4%)	1.11 (0.42 – 2.95)	0.836
Maximum number of diarrhea episodes in 24 h period				
3	3 (37.5%)	5 (62.5%)	Ref	Ref
4–5	58 (30.1%)	135 (69.9%)	0.71 (0.17 – 3.10)	0.655
5 or more	185 (28.8%)	457 (71.2%)	0.68 (0.16 – 2.85)	0.593
Experienced				
Yes	212 (30.2%)	491 (69.8%)	1.34 (0.88 – 2.04)	0.164
No	34 (24.3%)	106 (75.7%)	Ref	Ref
Duration of vomiting in days				
0	34 (24.3%)	106 (75.7%)	Ref	Ref
1	77 (26.2%)	217 (73.8%)	1.11 (0.69 – 1.76)	0.671
2	85 (36.6%)	147 (63.4%)	1.80 (1.13 – 2.88)	0.014*
3 or more	50 (28.2%)	127 (71.8%)	1.22 (0.74 – 2.04)	0.428
Maximum number of vomiting episodes in 24-h period				
0	34 (24.3%)	106 (75.7%)	Ref	Ref
1	6 (40.0%)	9 (60.0%)	2.08 (0.69 – 6.26)	0.194
2–4	113 (31.3%)	248 (68.7%)	1.42 (0.91 – 2.22)	0.123

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5 or more	93 (28.4%)	234 (71.6%)	1.24 (0.79 – 1.95)	0.356
Experienced fever				
Yes	183 (32.7%)	377 (67.3%)	1.69 (1.21 – 2.36)	0.002*
No	63 (22.3%)	220 (77.7%)	Ref	Ref
Dehydration as per Vesikari scoring				
Mild	6 (23.1%)	20 (76.9%)	Ref	Ref
Moderate	42 (26.1%)	119 (73.9%)	1.18 (0.44 – 3.13)	0.745
Severe	183 (29.8%)	432 (70.2%)	1.41 (0.56 – 3.57)	0.466
Very Severe	15 (36.6%)	26 (63.4%)	1.92 (0.63 – 5.85)	0.249
Treatment				
ORS	0	0	-	-
ORT	246 (29.2%)	597 (70.8%)	-	-
Length of hospital stay (IQR)				
0	10 (28.6%)	25 (71.4%)	Ref	Ref
1–2	39 (21.4%)	143 (78.6%)	0.68 (0.30 – 1.54)	0.357
3–4	123 (30.3%)	283 (69.7%)	1.09 (0.51 – 2.33)	0.831
5–6	57 (34.3%)	109 (65.7%)	1.31 (0.59 – 2.91)	0.512
7 or more	17 (31.5%)	37 (68.5%)	1.15 (0.45 – 2.92)	0.771
Outcome				
Discharged	220 (29.3%)	532 (70.7%)	Ref	Ref
Died	1	0	-	-
Others	25 (27.8%)	65 (72.2%)	0.93 (0.57 – 1.51)	0.771

Table 3 Genotype distribution in different years among children with rotavirus diarrhea identified by enzyme immunoassay (EIA)

Genotypes	2016	2017	2018	2019	Total
G10P[8]	-	1 (100.0%)	-	-	1 (0.4%)
G1P[6]	3 (75.0%)	-	-	1 (25.0%)	4 (1.6%)
G1P[8]	23 (69.7%)	9 (27.3%)	1 (3.0%)	-	33 (13.4%)
G2P[4]	3 (25.0%)	2 (16.7%)	2 (16.7%)	5 (41.7%)	12 (4.9%)
G3P[8]	32 (22.1%)	26 (17.9%)	56 (38.6%)	31 (21.4%)	145 (58.9%)
G9P[4]	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	3 (50.0%)	6 (2.4%)
G9P[8]	-	-	1 (100.0%)	-	1 (0.4%)
Mixed	6 (14.0%)	8 (18.6%)	21 (48.8%)	8 (18.6%)	43 (17.5%)
UTUT	1 (100.0%)	-	-	-	1 (0.4%)

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Total					246

Fig. 1 Seasonality of rotavirus diarrhea among hospitalized children under 5 years of age, KIMS, Odisha from 2016–19.

Fig. 2 Age distribution of children admitted with rotavirus positive and negative in 2016–19

Consent form for Publication

I Nirmal Kumar Mohakud give my consent for information about myself/my child or ward/my relative (circle as appropriate) to be published in

[Name of journal] IJP

[Manuscript number]

[Corresponding author] Nirmal Kumar Mohakud

NB: In cases where the patient has died or is incapable of giving consent, consent may be given by the next of kin. If the patient is under the age of 16, consent should be given by a parent or guardian.

I understand that the text and any pictures or videos published in the article

- 1. will be used only in educational publications intended for professionals
- Or
- 2. if the publication or product is published on an open access basis, I understand that it will be freely available on the internet and may be seen by the general public.

The pictures, videos and text may also appear on other websites or in print, may be translated into other languages or used for commercial purposes.

I understand that the information will be published without my/my child or ward's/my relative's (circle as appropriate) name attached, but that full anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

I have been offered the opportunity to read the manuscript.

I acknowledge that it is not possible to ensure complete anonymity, and someone may be able to recognize me. However, by signing this consent form I do not in any way give up, waive or remove my rights to privacy. I may revoke my consent at any time before publication, but once the information has been committed to publication ("gone to press"), revocation of the consent is no longer possible.

Name Nirmal Kumar Mohakud Date 20.11.2020 Signed

Author name..... Date..... Signed.....

Please keep this consent form in the patient's case files. The manuscript reporting this patient's details should state that 'Written informed consent for publication of their clinical details and/or clinical images was obtained from the patient/parent/guardian/ relative of the patient. A copy of the consent form is available for review by the Editor of this journal.